

Preferred Approaches and Students Perception in Teaching Literature Among the Junior High School Students in Jrmsu-Main, Dapitan City

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to assess the approaches to teaching English literature, students' perceptions of English literature, and its relationship to students' perceptions of Junior High School at Jose Rizal Memorial State University during the school year 2022-2023. A quantitative descriptive-correlational research design was employed in this study. Using frequency counting and percents, weighted mean, standard deviation, Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis test, and Spearman rank-order correlation, data were obtained from 157 junior high school students at Jose Rizal Memorial State University, Dapitan City Campus. The study found that the respondents perceived their preferred approaches to teaching English Literature as being very much preferred. In addition, the study discovered that the respondents' perceived level of perceptions of the teaching of English Literature is much preferred. Standard deviations less than 3.0 supported a high degree of homogeneity in their responses. The study found out that there is a significant difference in the perceived level of preferred approaches to teaching English is literature when the respondents were grouped in terms of age and year level and no significant difference in terms of sex. There is no significant difference in the perceived level of perceptions of the teaching of English literature when the respondents were grouped in terms of sex and age, and there is a significant difference in terms of year level. Furthermore, data analysis also revealed that preferred approaches to the teaching of English literature were positively connected with and substantially related to students' perceptions of teaching English. Hence, management strategy and working environments would be enhanced to boost the level of students' preferences in teaching English literature and students' perception in teaching English literature.

KEYWORDS: Approaches in Teaching English Literature, Perception in teaching English literature, Philippines

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Literature is essential in everyday life because it connects individuals with larger truths and ideas in society. This is why junior high school curricula include literature as one of their core subjects to address the interpersonal, informational, and aesthetic value of learning and literature in general. In addition, the literature component and language approach are designed to improve students' language and communication skills necessary to tackle the challenges and take advantage of 21st-century skills such as knowledge, communication skills, attitudes, and competencies (Parojenog, 2020). Based on the DepEd order no. 021 series of 2019, the curriculum shall be learner-centered and teacher-centered, inclusive, developmentally relevant, and appropriate teaching approaches. Learner-centered and teacher-centered approaches to education put the needs and interests of students at the center of the teaching and learning process. However, a lack of suitable reading materials might cause difficulties in the English literature classroom (Azmi et al., 2020). Moreover, in teaching literature in the classrooms, issues include an incorrect approach, a focus on how to answer previous question papers, a lack of appropriate reading materials, students' limited proficiency, and, at times, a lack of experience among teachers themselves (Hassan, Engku Atek, Latiff Azmi, & Azmi, 2020).

This study on preferred approaches to teaching literature and students' perceptions of these approaches is significant because it will help assess the current situations of both students and teachers in the Junior High School literature classes at Jose Rizal Memorial State University. Indeed, this study demonstrates the importance of literature in developing the student's language competency and cultural awareness of the target language and students' personal development awareness through studying literature. English literature can potentially be an essential tool for cultural adaptation and personal growth (Hassan, Engku Atek, Latiff Azmi, & Azmi, 2020). Furthermore, the importance of literature teaching approaches has drawn increasing attention, especially among students learning the aspects of literature (Atek, Hassan, Azmi, Yah, & Azmi, 2020). Moreover, the importance of learning outcomes in the literature classroom depends on the students' perceptions of integrating literature in the junior high classroom (Othman et al., 2015).

2.0 METHODOLOGY

The study included survey and descriptive-correlational research methods. The survey method will be employed since the researchers gathered data through a questionnaire checklist of approaches to teaching English literature and students' perceptions of English literature.

2.1 Research Environment

The study took off in Jose Rizal Memorial State University the premier university in Dapitan City, Province of Zamboanga del Norte, Philippines. It has a 157 Junior High School students.

2.2 Respondents of the Survey

The study respondents were a complete numeration of the one hundred fifty-seven (157) students of Junior High School during the school year 2022-2023. Table 1 below shows the distribution of respondents by two selected year level.

2.3 Research Instrument

The questionnaire used in the study consisted of three parts; 1. Demographic profile consist of sex, age and grade level; 2. Approaches to the teaching of English literature adopted from Atek, E. S. E., Isyaku, H., Nazri, L. A. M., Hazli, Y. M., & Jijiana, A. N. (2021) consist of twenty eight (28) items with six (6) indicators namely: information-based approach; paraphrastic approach; stylistic approach; language-based approach; personal-response approach; and moral-philosophical approach; 3. Students' perceptions in English literature adopted from Hassan, I., Engku Atek, E. S., Latiff Azmi, M. N., & Azmi, N. J. (2020) consist of five (19) items.

2.4 Data Gathering

A letter request, duly signed by the adviser, is sent to the Dean's office, Graduate School, Andres Bonifacio College, Inc., Dipolog City, requesting approval to field the study's instrument. Next, the researcher's letter and the Dean's endorsement letter are sent to the Office of the Vice Research and Extension. Next, the endorsement letter was forwarded to Research Ethics Committee, requesting ethics clearance to approve the study's instrument to field out. Finally, the Ethics Clearance is sent to the Heads/principals of different departments asking permission to administer the instrument.

2.5 Statistical Treatment

Presented below are the statistical tools utilized in the treatment and analysis of data gathered.

Frequency Counting and Percent. They are used to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age, and grade level.

Weighted Mean. This is used to quantify the respondents' ratings on the approaches to teaching English literature and students' perceptions of English literature. Presented below is the scoring guide in giving qualitative descriptions and interpretation of the responses of the items in approaches to teaching English literature and students' perceptions of English literature.

2.6 Ethical Consideration

This study obtained consent from Research Ethics Committee in Jose Rizal Memorial State University. The researcher reviewed the application of the principle of respect of persons by securing informed consent from the institution to distribute a research questionnaire free from technical terms that make it easier for the respondents to understand. The researcher will also solicit consent from the individual respondent during the conduct of the study. Respondents' identities are protected, their active participation guaranteed. This research ensured confidentiality of the respondents, which means that the respondents' identity would remain anonymous to everyone. At the end of the research, essential information that can support further research is preserved by the researcher.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the data in tabular form, analyzes, and interprets the data based on the statement of the problem in chapter 1.

Table 1: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex, Age, and Year Level

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	69	43.95
Female	88	56.05
Total	157	100.00
Age	Frequency	Percent

15 years & below	143	91.08
16-18 years old	14	8.92
Total	157	100.00
Grade Level	Frequency	Percent
Grade 7	37	23.57
Grade 8	34	21.66
Grade 9	38	24.20
Grade 10	48	30.57
Total	157	100.00

This table shows the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age, and year level. As shown in the table, 88 or 56.05% are females, 69 or 43.95% are males, 143 or 91.08% are 15 years & below, 14 or 8.92 are 16-18 years old, 37 or 23.57 are grade 7, 34 or 21.66 are grade 8, 38 or 24.20 are grade 9, and 48 or 30.57 are grade 10. This result indicates that the majorities of the respondents are female and 15 years old and below, and almost fairly distributed to the four grade levels.

The respondents' *sex* in the present study supported by Gordonas (2018) who indicated that majority of the respondents are female that comprises of (f = 68, 82.9%) while the male respondents comprise of (f = 14 or 17.1%).

The respondents' *age* in the present study supported by Gordonas (2018) who indicated that majority of the respondents are aged 18-20 years old that comprises of (f = 57, 69.5%) of the total sample of 82. Other respondents are aged 21 years old having the (f = 21, 25.6%) and lastly the respondents aged 17 years old and below having the (f = 4 or 4.9%).

The table shows the profile of the respondents in terms of year level. The finding contradicts the study of Hasan and Hasan (2019) who indicated that the majority of the respondents are 3rd year in secondary level in English literature subjects.

Table 2: Learners' Preferred Approaches to the Teaching of English Literature in terms of Information-Based

A. Information-Based	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Teacher guides students to identify and read informative extracts in the story.	4.54	0.57	Strongly Agree	Very Much Preferred
2. Teacher provides specific details on the literary elements found in the text.	4.29	0.64	Strongly Agree	Very Much Preferred
3. Teacher elicits information from students about the text.	4.26	0.71	Strongly Agree	Very Much Preferred
4. Teacher explains the main content of the text to the class.	4.73	0.46	Strongly Agree	Very Much Preferred
5. Teacher explains to the students with background information of the text.	4.52	0.57	Strongly Agree	Very Much Preferred
Overall Mean	4.47	0.62	Strongly Agree	Very Much Preferred

This table reveals the learners' preferred approaches to the teaching of English Literature in terms of information-based. The data show that the respondents very much preferred (mean=4.47, SD=0.62) the information-based approach of their teacher. This means that the teacher explains the main content of the text to the class, guides the students to identify and read informative extracts in the story, explains to the students with the background information of the text, provides specific details on the literary elements found in the text, and elicits information from the students about the text. The finding contradicts the study of Atek et al. (2020), which indicated that the moral-philosophical approach to teaching English literature is the most preferred approach among students, followed by information-based and language-based approaches.

The current finding agrees with the study of Alfian (2018), who indicated that learners preferred information-based approach to teaching English literature

Table 3: Learners' Preferred Approaches to the Teaching of English Literature in terms of Paraphrastic

B. Paraphrastic	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Teacher provides a written paraphrased version of a complementary reading text.	3.85	0.85	Agree	Much Preferred
2. Teacher solely uses a paraphrased version of the	3.88	0.73	Agree	Much Preferred

text.				
3. Teacher guides students to paraphrase the text.	4.15	0.82	Agree	Much Preferred
4. Teacher explains figurative and ambiguous language used in simple words.	4.45	0.69	Strongly Agree	Very Much Preferred
5. Teacher uses simple terms to explain what the story is about to students.	4.53	0.73	Strongly Agree	Very Much Preferred
Overall Mean	4.17	0.82	Agree	Much Preferred

This table depicts the learners' preferred approaches to the teaching of English Literature in terms of paraphrastic. The learners strongly agree that their teacher uses simple terms to explain what the story is about to the students and explains figurative and ambiguous language used in simple words. They agree that the teacher guides students to paraphrase the text, solely uses a paraphrased version of the text, and provides a written paraphrased version of a complementary reading text. Overall, the respondents agree (mean=4.17, SD=0.82) that they preferred a paraphrastic approach to the teaching of English Literature. The finding contradicts the study of Atek et al. (2020), which indicated that the moral-philosophical approach to teaching English literature is the most preferred approach among students, followed by information-based and language-based approaches.

Table 4: Learners' Preferred Approaches to the Teaching of English Literature in terms of Stylistic

C. Stylistic	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Teacher defines the correlation between language and content of information.	4.27	0.68	Strongly Agree	Very Much Preferred
2. Teacher compares the stylistic effect with other languages.	3.90	0.93	Agree	Much Preferred
3. Teacher explains the synonymous units of the words in the text.	4.17	0.77	Agree	Much Preferred
4. Teacher highlights the styles used in the text.	3.96	0.93	Agree	Much Preferred
5. Teacher asks students to explain the styles used in the text.	4.03	0.86	Agree	Much Preferred
Overall Mean	4.06	0.85	Agree	Much Preferred

Table 4 illustrates the learners' preferred approaches to the teaching of English and Literature in terms of stylistics. The respondents strongly agree that their teacher defines the correlation between language and the content of information. They agree that their compares stylistic effect with other languages, highlights the styles used in the text, asks questions to students to explain the styles used in the text, and teacher explains the synonymous units of the words in the text. Overall, the respondents much preferred (mean=4.06, SD=0.85) a stylistic approach to the teaching of English Literature. The current finding agrees with the study of Atek et al. (2021), who indicated that learners preferred a stylistic approach to teaching English literature. Similarly, Zokae, Zaferanieh, and Naseri (2012) who indicated that learners preferred stylistic approach to teaching English literature.

Table 5: Learners' Preferred Approaches to the Teaching of English Literature in terms of Language-Based

D. Language-based	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Teacher infers meaning from clues in the text.	4.17	0.77	Agree	Much Preferred
2. Teacher guides students to read between the lines	4.31	0.69	Strongly Agree	Very Much Preferred
3. Teacher asks students to make predictions on what will happen.	3.81	0.89	Agree	Much Preferred
4. Teacher guides students to express opinions towards a text.	4.34	0.73	Strongly Agree	Very Much Preferred
5. Teacher sets simple language activities in a literature lesson.	4.45	0.65	Strongly Agree	Very Much Preferred
Overall Mean	4.21	0.78	Strongly Agree	Very Much Preferred

This table displays the learners' preferred approaches to the teaching of English Literature in terms of language-based. The respondents strongly agree that their guide the student to read between the lines, guides students to express opinions towards a text, and teacher sets simple language activities in a literature lesson. They agree that their asks students to make predictions on what will happen and teacher inters meaning from clues in the text. Overall, the respondents strongly agree (mean=.21, SD=0.78) that language-based is very much preferred approach to the teaching of English Literature. The finding is supported by Atek et al. (2020), who indicated that the language-based approach to teaching English literature is preferred approach among students.

Table 6: Learners' Preferred Approaches to the Teaching of English Literature in terms of Personal Response

E. Personal-Response	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Teacher guides students to relate the themes to personal experiences.	4.22	0.87	Strongly Agree	Very Much Preferred
2. Teacher asks students to compare the text to any text they have read earlier.	4.10	0.80	Agree	Much Preferred
3. Teacher encourages students to respond to a text.	4.19	0.87	Agree	Much Preferred
4. Teacher encourages students to express feelings towards the issues raised in the text.	4.23	0.81	Strongly Agree	Very Much Preferred
Overall Mean	4.18	0.84	Agree	Much Preferred

This table portrays the learners' preferred approaches to the teaching of English Literature in terms of personal response. As can be gleaned in the table, the respondents strongly agree that their teacher guides students to relate the themes to personal experience and teacher encourages students to express feelings towards the issues raised in the text. They agree that their teachers ask students to compare the text to any text they have read teacher encourages students to respond to a text. Overall, the respondents agree that the personal-response approach to the teaching of English Literature is much preferred. The finding contradicts with the study of Atek et al. (2020), who indicated that the personal-response approach to teaching English literature is the least preferred approach among students.

Table 7: Test of Relationship between the Learners' Preferred Approaches to the Teaching of English Literature and Students' Perception in Teaching English Literature

Preferred Approaches to the Teaching of Literature	Correlation Coefficient	Students' Perception in Teaching Literature	Interpretation
Information-Based	Correlation Coefficient p-value	0.449 <0.01	Moderate Positive Correlation Significant
Paraphrastic	Correlation Coefficient p-value	0.345 <0.01	Positive Correlation Significant
Stylistic	Correlation Coefficient p-value	0.218 <0.01	Low Positive Correlation Significant
Language-Based	Correlation Coefficient p-value	0.208 <0.01	Low Positive Correlation Significant
Personal Response	Correlation Coefficient p-value	0.413 <0.01	Moderate Positive Correlation Significant
Moral-Philosophical	Correlation Coefficient p-value	0.281 <0.01	Low Positive Correlation Significant
Overall	Correlation Coefficient p-value	0.349 <0.01	Moderate Positive Correlation Significant

This table discloses the test of the relationship between the levels of learners' preferred approaches and their perception in the teaching of English Literature. Using Spearman rho, the result signifies that there exists a significant moderate positive correlation ($\rho=0.349$, $p<0.01$) between the levels of learners' preferred approaches and their perception in the teaching of English Literature. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that as the level of preference increases the level of perception also increases. This further indicates that the respondents' perception is affected by their preferences. The finding is supported by Hasan and Hasan (2019), who indicated that learners' perception of English literature influences their preferences in teaching English

Literature and teachers' teaching styles. Similarly, Wasti (2016) figure out that learners' perception greatly influences their interests and preferences in English literature. The current finding agrees with the study of Affendi and Aziz (2020), who indicated that learners' perception of English literature affect their preferences in teaching English Literature.

4.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations of the study.

This study aims to assess the approaches to teaching English literature, students' perceptions of English literature, and its relationship to students' perceptions of Junior High School at Jose Rizal Memorial State University during the school year 2022-2023.

With the help of the questionnaire checklist, survey and correlational research methodologies were used in the study. The key statistical methods employed in the study to help data analysis and interpretation were frequency count, percent, weighted mean, standard deviation, Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis test and Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient. The following findings and summary were revealed:

4.1 Findings and Summary

1. Females accounted for fifty-six point Zero five (56.05) percent of the surveyed respondents; majority of the respondents polled were the ages of 15 years and below; respondents under the age of between 16-18 accounted for eight point ninety-two percent (8.92); year level -grade 7 accounted for twenty-three point fifty-seven (23.57); grade 8 accounted for twenty-one point sixty-six percent (21.66); grade 9 accounted for twenty-four point twenty percent; and grade 10 accounted for thirty point fifty-seven percent 30.57.

2. JRMSU Junior High School learners were strongly agree and very much preferred in various approaches to the teaching of English Literature. However, learners were agree and much preferred at dealing with paraphrastic approach, stylistic, and personal response to the teaching of English literature.

3. JRMSU Junior High School students were agree and much preferred in perceptions to the teaching of English Literature. However, students were strongly agree and very much preferred at dealing in descriptors 1,2,3,4,9,10, 17, and 19.

4. Preferred approaches in teaching English literature among JRMSU Junior High School students were affected by their age and year level. However, students were unaffected by their sex.

5. Perception in teaching English literature among JRMSU Junior High School students were unaffected by their sex and age. However, students were affected by their year level.

6. JRMSU Junior High School preferred approaches to the teaching of English literature was positively connected with, and substantially related to students' perception in teaching English literature.

4.2 Conclusions

The study concludes that JRMSU Junior High School students surveyed demographic profiles such as age and year level affect preferred approaches to teaching English literature among students. However, sex does not affect preferred approaches to the teaching of English literature among students. Sex and age do not affect perception in teaching English literature among JRMSU Junior High School students. On the contrary, year level affects perception in teaching English literature among students. They have a very much preferred in various approaches to the teaching of English Literature. However, they have much preferred at dealing with paraphrastic approach, stylistic, and personal response to the teaching of English literature. They are also much preferred in perceptions to the teaching of English Literature. This justified that the teachers teaching approaches in English literature are well-taught and well-motivated. Furthermore, learner's preference in teaching English literature influences perception in teaching English literature. Moreover, those with high level of preferences in teaching English literature have a high level of perception in teaching English literature. Those with low level of preferences in teaching English literature have a low level of perception in teaching English literature.

4.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the study recommends the following:

1. The School Heads should send their teachers for seminar-workshops and trainings for further enhancement of knowledge in the use of the different teaching approaches.

2. The English teachers should use the different approaches in a classroom teaching which is most convenient towards learners specifically in learners' preferences in selected literary pieces. Teachers may employ other approaches in line with other student-centered approaches in teaching literature.

3. The students should learn variety of approaches employed by teachers for them to develop and sharpen their higher order thinking skills.

4. Future researchers should benchmark this study's findings from this generation and the upcoming one as their basis for future research implementation. In addition, future researchers should include variables not covered in this study to provide more information about six different approaches to teaching 21st Century Literature that is needed for the teacher to teach the subject effectively.

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